

Pre-Service Teachers' Knowledge, Skills, And Attitudes Towards Inclusive Sustainable Development In Education

Sijuade Adenike Florence, PhD

School of Education,
Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study assessed pre-service teacher knowledge, skills and attitude towards inclusive and sustainable development (ISD) in education among students of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design and was guided by five hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. Respondents were 385 students of colleges of education within Oyo State. They were selected using proportionate-stratified random sampling technique. Data was collected using Questionnaire on Knowledge, Skill and Attitude towards Inclusive Sustainable Development (QKESAISD) designed and validated by the researcher ($r = 0.73$). Data collected was analysed using frequency count, mean and standard, population t-test, independent t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA). Results shows that compared with the population, the pre-service teachers had high level of knowledge ($N = 385$, Mean = 12.7, SD = 1.45; $t = 31.47$) and high level of skills ($N = 385$, Mean = 12.73, SD = 1.13; $t = 46.58$) for ISD in education. The study found that the respondents had poor attitude towards ISD in education ($N = 385$, Mean = 8.85, SD = 1.838; $t = -64.15$). The study also revealed that significant difference in the knowledge of the pre-service year across levels of study (F-ratio (2,381) = 285.029; $p = .000$) with those in the final year showing the best knowledge but no significant difference in attitude across levels of study. The study suggests fostering attitudinal change among pre-service teachers, implementing targeted professional development for sustainability challenges, and consistently integrating sustainable development and inclusive education concepts into teacher education curricula at all levels.

Keywords: Attitude, Inclusive Education, Knowledge, Skills, Sustainable Development

INTRODUCTION

The concepts of inclusive education and sustainable development have gained significant global attention, particularly in light of efforts to ensure equitable access to quality education while addressing environmental sustainability challenges. Ogunyemi and Ifegbesan (1) emphasize the interconnection between these two concepts, highlighting the importance of pre-service teachers possessing a robust understanding of them, along with the necessary skills and attitudes to apply them effectively in diverse educational contexts. Inclusive education refers to the practice of creating educational settings that accommodate the diverse needs of all learners, regardless of their abilities, backgrounds, or challenges [2].

It is an approach that promotes equality, equity, and the right of every child to participate fully in learning opportunities. Sustainable development, on the other hand, entails meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs, emphasizing environmental protection, social equity, and economic growth [3]. The synergy between these two concepts gives rise to inclusive sustainable development (ISD), which fosters environments that are equitable, participatory,

and responsive to the needs of all learners while simultaneously promoting practices that lead to environmental stewardship and responsible citizenship.

Pre-service teachers, as the future workforce of educators, play a vital role in shaping educational practices, influencing attitudes, and fostering inclusive learning environments that support the goals of sustainable development.

They are expected to implement the principles of inclusivity and sustainability in education when they eventually become practicing teachers. Their training aims to equip them with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to design and deliver instruction that supports diverse learning needs while fostering environmental literacy and sustainability awareness.

Research has shown that pre-service teachers often encounter challenges in applying inclusive and sustainable development principles due to gaps in teacher preparation, limited exposure to practical strategies, or a lack of confidence in addressing diversity and sustainability issues [4]. Assessing their knowledge, skills, and attitudes is crucial for identifying these gaps and informing teacher education programs to ensure pre-service teachers are

well-prepared to address these global priorities. This assessment provides insights into their preparedness to create inclusive educational environments and contribute to sustainability goals, both in and outside the classroom. Understanding pre-service teachers' perspectives on inclusivity and sustainability is not only essential for fostering effective pedagogical strategies but also for advancing social equity and environmental sustainability goals. This assessment aligns with international initiatives, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which underscore the role of quality education in promoting inclusive learning and sustainable development by ensuring equal opportunities for all individuals. As pre-service teachers' attitudes, knowledge, and skills directly influence their instructional practices and engagement with students, evaluating these dimensions becomes a foundational step in preparing educators to support equity and sustainability in schools and communities.

Therefore, this study seeks to examine the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of pre-service teachers towards inclusive education and sustainable development to determine their preparedness for addressing these key global priorities. By exploring these dimensions, the research aims to uncover the extent to which pre-service teachers understand, value, and are equipped to implement inclusive and sustainable teaching practices. Furthermore, the findings can inform teacher training programs, policy decisions, and educational practices to strengthen pre-service teacher preparation, promote equity, and enhance sustainability awareness within education systems. Inclusive sustainable development in education prioritizes ensuring that all learners, regardless of their background, abilities, or circumstances, have equal access to quality education that empowers them to contribute to a sustainable future [5]. It involves creating an education system that is equitable, accessible, and relevant to the needs of all learners, while also promoting environmental sustainability and social responsibility [6]. The preparation of pre-service teachers to address the diverse needs of learners and contribute to sustainable development is a crucial area of focus in teacher education.

Pre-service teachers often possess a foundational understanding of inclusive education principles; however, significant gaps in the practical application of this knowledge hinder effective implementation. For instance, Mazzuki (6) highlights that while theoretical knowledge is frequently emphasized in teacher training programs, many pre-service teachers struggle to translate these concepts into effective classroom practices. This gap underscores the need for more practical, hands-on experiences during teacher preparation. Awareness of inclusive practices is pivotal in cultivating equitable learning environments. Pre-service teachers must adapt

lessons to accommodate diverse learners, including those with disabilities, linguistic differences, or marginalized identities [7]. Collaborating with professionals like special education teachers and counselors is essential for successfully implementing inclusive strategies. Increasing awareness through targeted training can better prepare pre-service teachers for inclusive settings. Building the skills for inclusive education demands innovative and experiential approaches. Service-learning, for instance, is an effective pedagogical strategy. It provides opportunities for pre-service teachers to engage directly with diverse learners, fostering a deeper understanding of inclusive education principles [11]. While pre-service teachers often lack adequate knowledge of specific Inclusive Sustainable Development Education (ISDE) concepts, particularly regarding environmental sustainability and social justice [2], they generally hold positive attitudes towards inclusive education [8].

Integrating eco-social justice and sustainability principles into training programs enhances pre-service teachers' assessment practices in inclusive settings. Embedding sustainability and justice themes into teacher education equips pre-service teachers to address complex challenges in inclusive classrooms while promoting broader sustainability goals [9]. This approach bridges theoretical understanding with practical applications. While pre-service teachers may have limited pedagogical skills for implementing ISDE practices, such as differentiated instruction and collaborative learning [1-], their level of study can influence skill development, with advanced students often possessing more refined abilities [5].

Pre-service teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education significantly impact their effectiveness in diverse classrooms. Negative attitudes, often stemming from a lack of exposure to inclusive practices, are prevalent among many pre-service teachers [11]. Reflective practices within service-learning experiences can challenge and transform these negative perceptions. Through reflection, pre-service teachers can critically examine their biases and develop a more positive and inclusive outlook. Integrating indigenous knowledge into science education fosters positive attitudes and enhances sustainability awareness among pre-service teachers. Incorporating indigenous perspectives not only enriches the curriculum but also cultivates a sense of respect and appreciation for cultural diversity and sustainability principles [12]. This approach highlights the potential for culturally responsive teaching to improve attitudes and commitment to inclusive and sustainable education. Assessing pre-service teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards inclusive and sustainable development is necessary to identify areas for improvement in teacher education programs.

The moderating role of level of study is significant. Early-stage pre-service teachers may have a foundational understanding of ISDE but lack practical experience, while advanced students may have a deeper theoretical knowledge and more developed skills but their attitudes may be influenced by prior experiences and beliefs [7]. The study is grounded in Vygotsky's social constructivist theory and Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour. Vygotsky's theory emphasizes the importance of social interaction and collaborative learning in knowledge construction.

In the Nigerian context, pre-service teachers can enhance their understanding of inclusive and sustainable practices through experiential learning, such as service-learning projects and mentorship opportunities. These activities provide real-world exposure, enabling teachers to apply theoretical knowledge in diverse classroom settings and collaborate with peers and experts to foster inclusive teaching strategies [13]. Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour (TPB) complements this by focusing on the role of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control in shaping intentions and behaviours. In Nigeria, the attitudes of pre-service teachers toward inclusive education significantly impact their willingness to implement such practices. Positive attitudes can be cultivated through targeted training programs that address biases and foster reflective practices. Subjective norms, such as institutional expectations and peer influence, play a critical role in shaping teachers' commitment to sustainability and inclusion. Enhancing perceived behavioural control through the provision of resources and strategies empowers pre-service teachers to effectively implement inclusive practices [14] [15].

The study aligns with the theme of the conference “*Capacity Building for Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education, Teacher Preparation and Language*” by addressing the foundational role that teacher preparation plays in fostering inclusive and sustainable educational practices. Pre-service teachers are the future workforce responsible for implementing inclusive and sustainable pedagogies in diverse classroom settings. By evaluating their current knowledge, skills, and attitudes, the study provides critical insight into the strengths and gaps within existing teacher education programs. This directly informs capacity-building strategies aimed at equipping educators with the competencies needed to promote equity, environmental awareness, and social justice in education. Furthermore, the study supports the broader goal of sustainable development by highlighting how inclusive practices can be nurtured from the early stages of teacher training.

This significance of the study lies in its capacity to assist educators in understanding how ready pre-service teachers are to help with inclusive and long-term growth in education. This study shows how well teacher education programmes are preparing teachers to support sustainability concepts and inclusive practices. It shows where things are going well and where there are gaps that could make it harder to reach Sustainable Development Goal 4, which calls for excellent, inclusive, and fair education for everyone. The results can help curriculum developers, policymakers, and teacher training programs redesign teacher education to better fit with global education goals. The study also adds to the larger conversation about sustainable development by showing how important teacher preparation is for making long-term changes in society. It also makes people more aware of how important it is to have educational methods that are open to diversity, care about the environment, and are socially responsible. The goal of this research is to help create a teaching workforce that is not only good at academics but also aware of social issues and dedicated to long-term educational success.

Statement of the Problem

Inclusive Sustainable Development (ISD) in education emphasizes equitable access to quality education for all learners, fostering environmental sustainability and social responsibility. However, the extent to which pre-service teachers in Oyo State possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to effectively implement ISD principles remains unclear. ISD in education demands a paradigm shift in teaching and learning. It requires educators with the knowledge, skills, and positive attitudes to create equitable and environmentally responsible learning environments. This study is crucial as it investigates the extent to which pre-service teachers in Oyo State possess these essential competencies. The findings of this research will provide valuable insights into the current state of pre-service teacher preparedness for ISD. This knowledge will inform the development of more effective teacher training programmes, ultimately leading to a more inclusive and sustainable education system that empowers all learners to thrive in a changing world.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to assess the knowledge, skills and attitude of pre-service teachers towards inclusive and sustainable development. Other objectives of the study are to:

1. investigate the level of knowledge of Oyo State pre-service teachers about inclusive sustainable development in education
2. find out the level of skills of Oyo State pre-service teachers in inclusive sustainable development in education

3. examine the attitude of Oyo State pre-service teachers towards inclusive sustainable development in education.
4. analyse if difference exist in knowledge of Oyo State pre-service teachers towards inclusive sustainable development in education across levels of study.
5. ascertain if difference exist in attitude of Oyo State pre-service teachers towards inclusive sustainable development in education across levels of study.

Research Questions

The following five hypotheses were guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between level of knowledge of Oyo State pre-service teachers about inclusive sustainable development in education and that of the population.
2. There is no significant difference between level of skills of Oyo State pre-service teachers about inclusive sustainable development in education and that of the population.
3. There is no significant difference between level of attitude of Oyo State pre-service teachers about inclusive sustainable development in education and that of the population.
4. There is no significant difference in knowledge of Oyo State pre-service teachers towards inclusive sustainable development in education across levels of study.
5. There is no significant difference exist in attitude of Oyo State pre-service teachers towards inclusive sustainable development in education across levels of study.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted survey research design to assess pre-service teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-demographic Information of the Respondents

Variable	N	%	Mean	SD
Gender				
Male	148	38.4		
Female	237	61.6	1.60	.490
Total	385	100.0		
Level of Study				
100 level	81	21.1		
200 level	141	36.6	2.25	.746
300 level	163	42.3		
Total	385	100.0		

Table 1 presents socio-demographic information of the respondents, likely pre-service teachers. It shows that the sample size is 385 individuals. In terms of gender, the majority of respondents are female (61.6%), while males constitute 38.4%. This suggests a female-dominated cohort. The table also provides

towards inclusive and sustainable development in Nigeria. The study area is Oyo State. The focus of the study is on colleges of education. Therefore, the target population are all 9786 students studying for Nigeria Certificate in Education in two colleges of education in Oyo State. The study sample comprised 385 derived using Yamane’s sampling formula. The sampling technique used is proportionate-stratified random sampling bearing in mind the socio-demographic characteristics such as gender and levels of study. A structured questionnaire tagged Questionnaire on Knowledge, Skill and Attitude towards Inclusive Sustainable Development (QKESAISD) developed by the researcher which covered the demographic details and knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward inclusive and sustainable development was used for the purpose of data collection. The questionnaire which has 10 items used closed-ended items measured on a Likert scale and open-ended questions for qualitative responses. Face and content validity of the instrument was ensured by vetting and contribution of experts in the field while it construct validity was carried out by two experts in Research, Measurement and Evaluation. The instrument was pilot-tested by prior administration to 20 individuals with similar characteristics being studied. Split-half reliability method was used and a reliability coefficient of 0.73 was derived.

Copies of the instrument was later administer to the respondents and retrieved. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant authority. Participants were assured of confidentiality, and pseudonyms were used to protect their identities. Participation was entirely voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any stage. Data collected was analysed using descriptive such as frequency count, mean and standard deviation as well as population t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA).

information on the level of study of the respondents. A majority of the respondents are in the 300 level (42.3%), followed by the 200 level (36.6%) and the 100 level (21.1%). This distribution indicates that the sample includes students from different stages of their teacher education programme.

Table 2: Population t-test Showing Knowledge of the Respondents about Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education

Variable	N	Mean	M. Diff	SD	df	t	Sig.	Remarks
Sample	385	12.7	2.37	1.46	385	31.47	.000	VGK

Note: SD = Standard Deviation; VGK = High knowledge

Table 1 presents the results of a population t-test, likely conducted to examine the knowledge of respondents about Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education. The sample size for this analysis is 385. The mean score for the sample on the knowledge measure is 12.7, with a standard deviation of 1.46. The mean difference between the sample and the population is 2.37, suggesting that the sample's knowledge score is higher than the population average. The t-value is 31.47, which is highly

significant ($p < .000$). This indicates that the difference between the sample mean and the population mean is statistically significant, providing strong evidence that the sample possesses very good knowledge about Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education compared to the broader population. This means that the level of knowledge of the pre-service teachers is not significantly low. Consequently, Hypothesis 1 is rejected.

Table 3: Population t-test Showing Level of Skill of the Respondents about Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education

Variable	N	Mean	M. Diff	SD	df	t	Sig.	Remarks
Skills	385	12.73	2.74	1.13	385	46.58	.000	VGL

Note: HS = VGL

Table 3 presents the results of a population t-test, likely conducted to examine the skills of respondents in relation to Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education. The sample size for this analysis is 385. The mean score for the sample on the skills measure is 12.73, with a standard deviation of 1.13. The mean difference between the sample and the population is 2.74, suggesting that the sample's skills score is higher than the population average. The t-value is

46.58, which is highly significant ($p < .000$). This indicates that the difference between the sample mean and the population mean is statistically significant, providing strong evidence that the sample possesses high skills (HS) in relation to Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education compared to the broader population. This means that the level of skills of the pre-service teachers is not significantly low. Consequently, Hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Table 4: Population t-test Showing Attitude of the Respondents about Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education

Variable	N	Mean	M.Diff	SD	df	t	Sig.	Remarks
Skills	385	8.89	-1.113	1.838	385	-64.15	.079	PA

Note: PA = Poor Attitude

Table 4 presents the results of a population t-test, likely conducted to examine the attitudes of respondents towards inclusive sustainable development in education. The sample size for this analysis is 385. The mean score for the sample on the attitude measure is 8.89, with a standard deviation of 1.838. The mean difference between the sample and the population is -1.113, suggesting that the sample's attitude score is lower than the population average. The t-value is -64.15, which is not significant (p

$< .079$). This indicates that the difference between the sample mean and the population mean is not statistically significant, providing strong evidence that the sample possesses a poor attitude (PA) towards Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education compared to the broader population. This means that the attitude of the pre-service teachers is significantly poor. Consequently, Hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Table 5a: AMOVA of Difference in Knowledge of Pre-Service Teachers towards Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education across Levels of Study

Knowledge	ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Between Groups	470.147	2	235.074	285.029	.000	
Within Groups	314.325	381	.825			
Total	784.472	383				

Table 5b: Scheffe’s Post-Hoc Analysis

Dependent Variable: Knowledge		Multiple Comparisons		
Scheffe				
(I) Level of study	(J) Level of study	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
100 level	200 level	-1.637*	.134	.000
	300 level	-3.055*	.131	.000
200 level	100 level	1.637*	.134	.000
	300 level	-1.418*	.105	.000
300 level	100 level	3.055*	.131	.000
	200 level	1.418*	.105	.000

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 5A and 5B present the results of statistical analyses investigating potential differences in pre-service teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards Inclusive Sustainable Development (ISD) across different levels of study. Table 5A is an ANOVA which examines knowledge. It shows significant differences in knowledge scores between different levels of study. To pinpoint which groups differ, a post-hoc analysis (Scheffe test) was

conducted. The Scheffe post-hoc results reveal a clear trend: students in higher levels of study demonstrated significantly higher knowledge scores compared to those in lower levels. Specifically, 300-level students had significantly higher knowledge than both 100-level and 200-level students. This suggests that the teacher education programme effectively increases pre-service teachers' understanding of ISD concepts as they progressed through their studies. Hypothesis 4 is therefore rejected.

Table 6: ANOVA of Difference in Attitude of Pre-Service Teachers towards Inclusive Sustainable Development in Education across Levels of Study

ANOVA						
Attitude	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Between Groups	3.043	2	1.522	.448	.639	
Within Groups	1294.257	381	3.397			
Total	1297.300	383				

Table 6 presents the results of an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) conducted to investigate differences in pre-service teachers' attitudes towards inclusive sustainable development (ISD) across different levels of study. The F-ratio is .448 at degree of freedom 2, 368, with p-value of 0.639. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there are significant differences in attitudes towards ISD among pre-service teachers across different levels of study.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The researcher investigated pre-service teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards inclusive sustainable development in education. The study found that pre-service teachers demonstrated a high level of knowledge about inclusive sustainable development compared to the broader population. This aligns with previous research indicating that teacher preparation programs effectively integrate sustainability principles into their curricula [9]. This knowledge foundation positions pre-service teachers as potential agents for implementing inclusive and sustainable educational strategies. Furthermore, their positive attitudes and strong skills towards these concepts underscore their readiness to promote inclusive sustainability in diverse learning environments. UNESCO (10) emphasizes the importance of fostering positive attitudes and

enhancing relevant skill sets to translate knowledge into effective classroom practices.

The study also revealed that pre-service teachers exhibited a very good level of skills related to inclusive sustainable development. These skills encompass integrating sustainability principles into educational planning, curriculum development, and classroom management, as well as fostering inclusive learning environment [10]. These skills align with global recommendations for sustainable development, such as SDG 4, which focuses on inclusive and equitable quality education [10]. Research by Hsieh *et al.* (5) and Anor (3) supports these findings, emphasizing the role of teacher preparation programs in equipping pre-service teachers with the practical capabilities to implement sustainability in diverse educational settings.

However, the study also revealed a concerning finding: pre-service teachers had a poor attitude towards inclusive sustainable development compared to the broader population. This may be influenced by limited practical exposure to sustainability initiatives, a lack of confidence in implementing sustainability practices, or the perception of sustainability goals as complex and difficult to integrate [3]. Previous studies have highlighted that attitudes toward sustainability are often shaped by gaps in teacher education programs, which may emphasize theoretical knowledge without sufficiently addressing

practical applications and context-based learning experiences [7].

The study further revealed that the level of knowledge of the pre-service teachers is affected by level of study, with final-year students demonstrating significantly better knowledge than earlier-year students. This suggests that progression through the teacher education program enhances knowledge acquisition in sustainability principles and inclusive practices [4], [7]. However, the attitude of the pre-service teachers remained significantly poor irrespective of their level of study. This indicates that advancing through different stages of teacher education does not necessarily translate into improved attitudes toward sustainability and inclusivity [12], [7]. To address these findings, teacher preparation programs should adopt a more integrated and practical approach by creating opportunities for pre-service teachers to engage in experiential learning and community-based sustainability projects [1]. Transformative education strategies that emphasize reflective teaching practices and hands-on application may shift attitudes, fostering motivation and readiness to adopt inclusive and sustainable strategies in professional contexts [15]. By addressing these challenges, teacher preparation programs can ensure that pre-service teachers adopt positive attitudes and become proactive agents of change within the educational system.

SUMMARY

The study investigated pre-service teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward inclusive sustainable development in education and revealed important patterns. The findings indicated that pre-service teachers exhibited very good knowledge and skills related to inclusive sustainable development in education compared to the broader population, suggesting the effectiveness of teacher preparation programmes in equipping them with relevant theoretical understanding and practical competencies. Additionally, the study found that the level of knowledge improved with progression through the levels of study, with final-year pre-service teachers performing significantly better than their counterparts in earlier years. Despite their strong knowledge and skills, pre-service teachers demonstrated poor attitudes toward inclusive sustainable development, a trend that remained unchanged regardless of their level of study. This highlights that while knowledge and skills are being developed through teacher training programmes, attitudes are not positively shifting as expected. These findings suggest the need for teacher education programmes to incorporate practical, reflective, and context-based learning experiences to foster positive attitudes and confidence in implementing inclusive sustainable development strategies. This will better prepare pre-

service teachers to act as agents of change in promoting sustainability and inclusivity within educational settings.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of pre-service teachers regarding inclusive sustainable development in education. The results indicate that pre-service teachers possess very good knowledge and skills in this area compared to the broader population, suggesting that teacher preparation programmes effectively equip them with the theoretical understanding and practical competencies necessary for implementing sustainability and inclusivity in educational settings. Additionally, the study found that the level of knowledge of pre-service teachers improves with higher levels of study, with final-year students demonstrating significantly better knowledge than those in earlier years. This progression highlights the role of advanced study and deeper engagement with sustainability concepts in enhancing understanding and readiness.

However, despite their strong knowledge and skills, pre-service teachers displayed poor attitudes toward inclusive sustainable development, a finding that remained consistent regardless of their level of study. This suggests that theoretical learning and skill development alone may not be sufficient to foster positive attitudes. Addressing this gap will require teacher education programmes to incorporate practical, hands-on learning opportunities and reflective practices that promote engagement and confidence in applying sustainability strategies. These findings underscore the need for transformative and experiential approaches in pre-service teacher education to support positive attitude change, enabling pre-service teachers to become effective change agents for inclusive and sustainable education.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study has some limitations. First, the study has limited geographical coverage as it covered only pre-service teachers in Oyo State, limiting its generalizability to other region. Secondly, the study focused on pre-service teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes, but did not directly assess their actual classroom practices related to inclusive and sustainable development education. Finally, the survey research design adopted in the study limits the ability to establish causal relationships between variables.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Efforts must be made to engender attitudinal change in pre-service teachers. This can be

achieved through journaling, peer discussions, and guided problem-solving sessions which can help pre-service teachers examine their attitudes toward sustainability, address misconceptions, and build a stronger sense of confidence in implementing sustainability strategies.

2. Teacher training programmes should include targeted professional development programmes that focus on the practical challenges of sustainability implementation and equip pre-service teachers with strategies to overcome barriers, build motivation, and strengthen their role as change agents.
3. Sustainability and inclusive education content should be consistently embedded across all levels of teacher education curricula. This would ensure that all pre-service teachers, regardless of their level of study, receive comprehensive, consistent, and practical engagement with these concepts.
4. Colleges of education should create opportunities for pre-service teachers to collaborate on projects focused on sustainability and inclusive development so as to enhance both skills and attitudes.

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